

User stories for the Data Usage Typology

FORCE11 Data Usage Typologies Working Group

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Researchers

As a researcher, I would like to see how others have used datasets I published, so that I can improve my future data collection and documentation practices.

As a researcher, I would like to see how the datasets I produced have been used to describe their usage and impact in my periodic activity reports and applications for positions and promotions.

As a cross-disciplinary researcher, I would like to map the disciplines from which the data I use originate, the repositories they come from and the countries where these repositories sit.

As a meta-researcher, I would like to have defined use types of data so that I can incorporate this as part of my research projects looking at data use practices.

As a researcher, I want to know if other researchers at my university have already used a dataset that I think is relevant to my research.

Evaluators (e.g. institutional administrators, funders, editors)

As a research performing institution, I would like to map the data services we support and the way these services are used to identify successes and issues, and the measures to implement to amplify the successes and deal with the issues.

As a research performing institution, I would like to track data reuse of datasets shared by my institution's researchers, so that I can demonstrate impact and advocate more open data practices.

As a research performing institution, I would like to map the data-providing services we support, the way these services are used and the geographical extent of their usage to measure my impact in the data pillar of Open Science.

As a funder, we would like to have information about the ways in which datasets from projects we funded have been used, so that we can identify datasets that are being widely used by different groups and for new research endeavours.

As a funder, we would like to know how the data produced by the projects we funded are used to eventually update the guidelines we provide to projects, so that the usage of their data is facilitated.

As a policy maker/government, I would like to map the data services available in my country and the way they are used, by whom and for which aim, to identify successes and gaps, and the measures to implement to amplify the successes and deal with the gaps.

As a policy maker promoting Open Science, I would like to know the data produced in my country that are publicly available and reusable, for which aims and in which countries and how the data is used to measure my contribution to the data pillar of Open Science. [data sharing and data discovery would rather be upstream of the data use]

As an institution/funder/policy maker/journal/individual advocating for Open Science, I would like to have evidence whether data sharing is actually worth it so that we can influence other stakeholders to adopt data sharing policies which maximize data impact

Infrastructure providers (e.g. publishers, repositories, services that support data ecosystem)

As a repository or service provider, I would like to understand the ways in which researchers interact with the data products my organization provides so that we can inform future service improvements, adapt to current research trends, and ensure maximum utility of our resource to the communities we serve.

As a repository, I would like to tag datasets with typical usage and activities in metadata, so that users can better discover datasets aligned with their research tasks.

As a repository or research facility provider, I would like to have information about the different ways in which users of our platforms are using our datasets and where the users come from, so that I can include this information in my reports to our funder(s) and for future funding requests.

As a research facility or repository provider, I would like to be able to capture and share information on whether the use of data was by the creators themselves or by others, to enrich the information about research content with signals for its value and reach.

As a research facility or repository provider, I would like to capture the usage of my datasets in “non-research” activities to demonstrate my societal impact.

As someone who helps researchers share their research data, I would like to have information about the impact of my researchers' data in order to show them that their efforts to make their data more findable and reusable is worth the effort and to evaluate the impact of data services support.

As a data aggregator, I would like to measure and report impact more accurately and make meaningful comparisons. I would like to be able to easily tell if the data being used is generated as part of the same work and by the same authors—or if they used data produced by someone else.

As a data aggregator, I would like to know how much data in a cited dataset is used, and if not all data, why not.

As a journal publisher, I would like to know how inter/cross-disciplinary our content is (via the reuse of data) so that I can see if we are meeting the mission of the journal and modify the editorial strategy as needed.

As a journal publisher, I would like to detect highly-cited datasets (or those with high potential to become such) to be able to contact authors potentially interested in publishing data articles.

As a journal publisher we would collect/capture data usage type to ensure it can be included in the article's metadata to enhance the citation to the data.